

Investigation of Solids and Surfaces by Photoacoustic Spectroscopy†

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After presenting the essentials of the principles and instrumentation involved in photoacoustic spectroscopy, a variety of studies of solids and surfaces carried out by this technique are reported. Some of the important aspects of the spectroscopy examined are signal saturation, intensity enhancement and fluorescence quenching. Applications to the study of amorphous solids, phase transitions and surfaces are discussed.

PHOTOACOUSTIC spectroscopy has emerged to become a very useful absorption spectroscopic technique in recent years. The technique is based on the photoacoustic effect discovered by Graham Bell¹ over a century ago. Photoacoustic effect in gases has been understood almost since its discovery, but it is only in the last few years that a proper theoretical treatment of photoacoustic effect in solids has been possible². After the absorption of radiation by a solid sample, the excited state can decay radiatively or non-radiatively; if the radiation is modulated, the heat given out during non-radiative decay will also be modulated. The heat diffusion into the coupling fluid (ordinarily ambient air in the cell) produces pressure variation with the same frequency as the frequency of modulation (f) and this can be detected by a microphone. The direct correspondence between the light absorbed by the sample and the intensity of the sound signal picked up by the microphone makes photoacoustic spectroscopy a viable alternative to conventional optical spectroscopy. Photoacoustic spectroscopy has advantages over the optical technique in certain situations. For example, in the case of solids³, scattering by powder samples does not impose limitations in photoacoustic spectroscopy (PAS). Furthermore, PAS is also a surface-sensitive technique³, requiring hardly a monolayer coverage of the absorbing substance. In this article we shall discuss the principles and applications of photoacoustic spectroscopy with particular reference to solids and surfaces.

Theoretical model :

The model that has been most useful in understanding PAS of solids is the one due to Rosenzweig and Gersho⁴ (RG). The RG model is based on a one-dimensional analysis of the production of a PA signal in a cylindrical cell and gives an exact equation for the magnitude and phase of the signal in terms of the thermal, optical and geometrical properties of cell, sample and the ambient gas. The sample of thickness, l , is mounted on a backing material as shown in Fig. 1. If the backing material and the gas are non-absorbing, the following thermal

Fig. 1. Cross sectional view of the photoacoustic cell.

diffusion equation (where, the distance x changes from zero at the surface to negative values inside the solid) can be written

$$\frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial x^2} = \frac{1}{\alpha_1} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} - A \exp(\beta x) [1 + \exp(i\omega t)]$$

$$\text{where, } A = \frac{\beta I_0 \eta}{2K_1} \quad (1)$$

The various terms in equation (1) are defined as follows: θ = temperature, I_0 = intensity of incident light, η = efficiency of conversion of light into heat, K_1 = thermal conductivity ($\text{cal cm}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$), ρ_1 = density (g cm^{-3}), C_1 = heat capacity ($\text{cal g}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$), α_1 = thermal diffusivity ($= K_1/\rho_1 C_1$) ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$), $\mu_1 = (1/\alpha_1)$ = thermal diffusion length ($= 2\alpha_1/\omega$)^{1/2} (cm), ω = chopping frequency ($= 2\pi f$) (Hz).

The subscript $i=1, 2$ and 3 refers to the solid, gas and backing, respectively. The real part of the solution of equation (1) represents the temperature-variation in the cell relative to the ambient. On applying the boundary conditions (*viz.* (i) cell walls are at the ambient temperature and (ii) there is continuity of temperature and flux at the surface) to the a.c. and d.c. components of the time-dependent spatial temperature variation, we obtain the time dependent and independent temperature distribution in the cell. The real part of the a.c. component gives the temperature variation in the gas,

$$T_{a.o}(x,t) = \exp(-a_2 x) [\theta' \cos(\omega t - a_2 x) - \theta'' \sin(\omega t - a_2 x)] \quad (2)$$

† Dedicated to Professor Sadhan Basu on the occasion of his 65th birthday.
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where, θ' and θ'' are the real and the imaginary parts of θ which determine the in-phase and quadratic components. The time-dependent temperature variation attenuates rapidly to zero at a distance $2\pi\mu_2$. The boundary layer of thickness $2\pi\mu_2$ responds thermally to temperature acting as an acoustic piston for the gas column.

The displacement of the boundary layer $\delta x(t)$ can be determined by knowing the average temperature within the boundary layer,

$$\delta x(t) = \frac{\theta\mu_2}{\sqrt{2T_0}} \exp [i(\omega t - \pi/4)] \quad (3)$$

where, T_0 is the sum of the ambient and d.c. temperatures at the surface. Assuming that the rest of the gas responds to the action of the acoustic piston adiabatically, the incremental pressure $\delta p(t)$ is given by,

$$\delta p(t) = Q \exp [i(\omega t - \pi/4)]$$

where $Q = \frac{\gamma p_0 I_0}{\sqrt{2} l_2 T_0 a_2}$ (4)

γ being the ratio of specific heats. The actual pressure variation is given by the real part of equation (4),

$$Q = Q' + iQ'' \quad (5)$$

we thus see that Q represents the complex envelope of sinusoidal pressure variation

$$Q = \frac{\beta I_0 \gamma p_0}{\sqrt{22T_0 K_1 l_2 a_2 (\beta^2 - \sigma^2)}} \frac{(r-1)(b+1)e^{\sigma l_1} - (r+1)(b-1)e^{-\sigma l_1} + 2(b-r)e^{-\beta l_1}}{(g+1)(b+1)e^{\sigma l_1} - (g-1)(b-1)e^{-\sigma l_1}} \quad (6)$$

where, $b = K_2 a_2 / K_1 a_1$; $g = K_2 a_2 / K_1 a_1$; $r = (1-i)\beta/a_1^2$ and $\sigma = (1+i)a_1$. Equation (6) can be employed to evaluate the magnitude and phase of the acoustic pressure wave in the cell.

Aamodt and others⁵ have modified the RG model by applying the Navier-Stokes equation for heat conduction. McDonald and Wetsel⁶ have included corrections for mechanical vibration of the sample at high modulation frequencies.

Instrumentation :

A photoacoustic spectrometer for the study of solids is not very different from the conventional optical spectrometer. It consists of a radiation source, a monochromator, a light modulator, a sample cell fitted with a microphone (detector) and the data collection and processing system (recorder, microprocessor *etc.*). Since photoacoustic detection involves the detection of sound rather than photons, care has to be exercised to minimise external noise.

The PA signal varies inversely with the gas volume, v , in the cell and one has to therefore minimise v , without damping the acoustic signal. Since only the boundary layer of the gas $2\pi\mu_2$ responds thermally, l_2 should be greater than μ_2 ; at the same

time, l_2 has to be kept small to minimise thermo-viscous damping. The optimal value of l_2 is 0.1-0.2 cm. The signal can be improved by employing low temperatures and high gas pressures; use of gases with high thermal conductivity can also improve the signal. Signal enhancement has also been accomplished by using volatile liquids in the cell⁷. Noise can be reduced by using polished materials; the signal to noise ratio is enhanced by the use of materials which undergo a small temperature rise for large heat input. Scattered light should be allowed to escape (by proper cell design) before it is absorbed by the walls, microphone *etc.* Acoustic isolation helps in avoiding spurious signals while vibration-free mounting is useful to avoid effects due to mechanical vibrations. The design of the cell depends on the physical nature of the sample. For variable temperature measurements, the microphone would have to be kept outside the sample chamber and connected by an acoustic-proof capillary. Fast cooling or heating adversely affects the microphone due to pressure surges; condensation of water should be avoided.

Solids in the form of powders (or powder compacts) can be readily studied by PAS. Films deposited on quartz plates as well as smears can also be examined. Substances adsorbed on solid surfaces (from solution or some other means) can also be investigated.

An indigenous photoacoustic spectrometer for the uv-visible range : The block diagram of a spectrometer indigenously built in our laboratory⁸ is shown in Fig. 2. Light from a high pressure xenon lamp is focussed onto a GM250 monochromator fitted

Fig. 2. Block diagram of the single-beam photoacoustic spectrometer fabricated by the authors.

with a Schoeffel holographic grating. A tungsten lamp would suffice if only the visible region is of interest. The light emerging from the monochromator passes through a chopper (PAR 194A) capable of providing frequencies in the 10-1 000 Hz range. The PA cell is an air-tight aluminium chamber which has been designed taking the various factors mentioned earlier into account. A condenser microphone (GR 1961) with a flat frequency

response in the range 10-2 000 Hz is attached to the rear side of the sample chamber with an air-tight sealing. The signals from the microphone and reference from the chopper are fed to a lock-in-amplifier (PAR 124A) and the output of the tuned amplifier gives the sound signal which is recorded as a function of the wavelength of light.

Variable temperature measurements can be carried out by employing cells described by Ganguly and Rao³. The cell for low-temperature measurements has been designed in such a way that the sample is surrounded by a cold finger which in turn is connected to liquid nitrogen reservoir, the whole system being kept under vacuum. A stainless steel capillary is welded to the sample holder to provide passage of the sound to the microphone while a 3-way stopcock provides the necessary equilibrium pressure during temperature changes. In the high-temperature cell, the microphone is kept away from the sample chamber but connected with a glass capillary. Temperature is sensed by a chromel-alumel thermocouple placed near the sample. Temperatures only upto 550 K could be attained since a teflon O-ring was used in the spectrometer.

Electronic spectra of solids :

Electronic absorption spectra of solid substances can be recorded by the PAS technique provided the transitions do not involve radiative decay. The substance can be crystalline or amorphous, single crystal or polycrystalline ; it can even be in the form of a gel. In Fig. 3 we show the unnormalised PA spectra of Nd_2O_3 and NdAlO_3 in the visible

Fig. 3. Unnormalised spectra of NdIII compounds : (---) Nd_2O_3 and (—) NdAlO_3 , $\Delta \lambda$ 10 nm, f 28 Hz.

region ; the slight differences arise from the different modes of de-excitation⁹. In Fig. 4 we show the spectra of single crystal and polycrystalline samples of NaNO_2 in the uv region ; we see little difference between the spectra as indeed expected. PAS is ideally suited to record the spectra of solids which are sparingly soluble in solvents. However, PAS has no particular advantage over transmission

Fig. 4. Normalised spectra of NaNO_2 (intensities normalised to be equal at 360 nm) : (---) powdered sample and (—) single crystal, $\Delta \lambda$ 5 nm, f 40 Hz.

optical spectra (recorded with KBr pellets or oil mulls between quartz plates) and diffuse reflectance spectra.

Signal saturation :

The active layer in the solid responding thermally in PAS has a thickness of $2\pi\mu_1$. As the thermal oscillations, generated at a distance x from the surface, move towards the surface, their amplitude attenuate exponentially⁸ as $\exp(-x/\mu_1)$. For $x = 2\pi\mu_1$, the attenuation becomes $\exp(-2\pi)$. If the sample thickness is greater than $2\pi\mu_1$ and the surface of the sample is in contact with the gas, the heat distribution is given by $\beta \exp(-\beta s)$, where, s is the distance from the surface and β is the absorption coefficient. The increase in the PA signal accompanying an increase in absorptivity can be attributed to the movement of the heat distribution into the active layer and closer to the surface ; this prevails till $\beta^{-1} = \mu_1$, when the heat distribution moves completely inside the active layer and saturation sets in (Fig. 5). Further increase in β will eventually lead to full saturation⁸ when $10\beta^{-1} = \mu_1$.

According to the RG model, saturation can be avoided by changing the frequency of modulation such that $\mu_1 < \beta^{-1}$. This is not however suitable for materials with $\beta \geq 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ as one would require frequencies greater than 10^4 Hz to bring them out of the saturation regime ; use of such a high frequency also leads to enormous reduction of the signal to noise ratio. Proper sample preparation can avoid saturation⁹ by bringing down the sample

Fig. 5. Attenuation of heat distribution in the solid sample after light absorption for various β values⁹. The boundary layer ($2\pi\mu_1$) is indicated ($\beta_1 < \beta_2 < \beta_3 < \beta_4$).

size to less than β . This can be done for example by dispersing the absorbing substance in a non-absorbing matrix or over the surface of a non-absorbing solid; another possibility is to prepare a thin layer of the sample by vacuum or solution technique. In Fig. 6 we show the use of such techniques in the case of tetraphenylporphyrin⁹.

Intensity enhancement :

Since PAS is specially useful in providing information on materials of low absorption coefficient or opaque substances, it would be particularly beneficial if the limits of detection can be extended by some means. The PA signal from solids can be enhanced several-fold by placing volatile liquids⁷, such as diethyl ether or acetone in the cell; the enhancement which is more marked for low β and high f depends upon the vapour pressure of the liquid. In order to hold the liquids, the PA cell sample holder is made of two concentric portions, the outer portion containing a non-absorbing solid (e.g. Al_2O_3) soaked in the liquid. In Fig. 7 we show the PA spectra of $Nd_3Al_5O_{13}$ in air and in the presence of diethyl ether to illustrate the intensity enhancement in the presence of a volatile liquid. The intensity enhancement is found to vary linearly with the vapour pressure. The enhancement is likely to be due to the desorption and adsorption of the adsorbed vapours on the solid surface, accompanying the thermal oscillations. The factors responsible for the intensity enhancement are the efficient heat transfer arising from the reduction in the thermal diffusion length in the gas phase (μ_2) and the increase in the number of gas molecules in the gas phase due to desorption. PAS can also be employed to investigate liquid-liquid interfaces where again intensity enhancement by volatile liquids can be exploited.

Fluorescence quenching :

If the decay after optical absorption is through a radiative process such as fluorescence, one would

expect the PA signal to have little or no intensity. Quenching of luminescent pathways would however give rise to PA signal as illustrated in the case of Ho_2O_3 and Ho_2O_3-Co, F (Fig. 8). The doped sample exhibits additional lines which arise from the known energy levels of Ho^{III} ; obviously, these extra lines were not present in the spectrum of pure Ho_2O_3 due to fluorescent decay¹⁰.

Fluorescent quantum yields, η , of solid materials are difficult to determine compared to solutions because the number of quanta absorbed from a monochromatic radiation cannot be compared with the number of quanta of polychromatic radiation emitted due to geometrical problems associated with solid samples. Employing the PA saturation technique, η can be determined for solid luminescent

Fig. 6. Photoacoustic spectra of tetraphenylporphyrin⁹ (TPP) : (a) 0.35 wt% of TPP mechanically dispersed in $BaSO_4$ by cogrinding, (b) 0.1 wt% of TPP chemically dispersed on $BaSO_4$ by slurry method, (c) 0.3 μg of TPP smear on quartz plate, and (d) optical spectrum of TPP.

Fig. 7. PA spectrum of $\text{Nd}_2\text{Al}_2\text{O}_7$ in the presence of air (bottom curve) and ether (top curve). The reference spectrum of carbon black is also shown.

Fig. 8. PA spectra of pure and doped holmium oxides¹⁰

samples¹¹. The PA signal characteristic of a fluorescent sample can be written as,

$$I_F = k_F p_F \left[1 - \eta + \eta \left(\frac{\nu_0 - \nu_F}{\nu_0} \right) \right] \quad (7)$$

where, k_F is a constant characteristic of the thermal properties of the sample and the instrumental characteristics, p_F is the power absorbed by the sample, and ν_0 and ν_F are the excitation and emission frequencies, respectively. For a non-fluorescent sample, the PA signal is given by,

$$I_{NF} = k_{NF} p_{NF} \quad (8)$$

we therefore obtain,

$$\frac{I_F}{I_{NF}} = \frac{k_F p_F}{k_{NF} p_{NF}} \left(1 - \frac{\lambda_0}{\lambda_F} \eta \right) \quad (9)$$

where, λ_0 and λ_F represent the excitation and emission wavelengths, respectively. For saturated signals, we can assume¹¹ that $p_F = p_{NF}$. Equation (9) then becomes,

$$\frac{I_F}{I_{NF}} = \frac{k_F}{k_{NF}} \left(1 - \eta \frac{\lambda_0}{\lambda_F} \right) \quad (10)$$

We can calculate η from the known values of λ_0 and λ_F and measured values of I_F and I_{NF} . It is obvious that a plot of I_F/I_{NF} against λ is nothing but the normalised spectrum using carbon black. Particle size seems to affect the value of η thus obtained¹¹. PAS can however be fruitfully employed to determine η in solution media^{12,13}.

Solid state reactions :

Reactions of solids can be followed by PAS provided there are appropriate absorption bands of the reactants or/and products in the uv or visible region. Chance and Shand¹⁴ have employed PAS to carry out photocalorimetry. They have made use of the fact that the heat due to light absorption as well as the heat liberated in the reaction are measured in PAS. Accordingly, in a polymerisation reaction, the time-dependence of the intensity of the PAS bands would depend on the heat of the reaction relative to the heat associated with photo-absorption; the rate of polymerisation would determine the heat of polymerisation at a given time. In PAS, the intensity of a band depends on the power absorbed and the efficiency of conversion of light into heat, η , while in optical spectroscopy (OS) the intensity depends only on the power absorbed. For a substance with $\eta=1$, therefore, a plot of (PAS)/(OS) vs wavelength should be a straight line with zero slope. If $\eta \neq 1$, the plot will give the wavelength dependence of the photo-reaction or the action spectrum. Such action spectra have been recorded for the polymerisation of diacetylenes¹⁵.

Amorphous solids :

Optical spectroscopic characterisation of many of the amorphous solids by conventional techniques is rendered difficult due to the highly reflecting and absorbing nature of these materials. Optical studies on such solids are therefore made with thin films which are difficult to prepare. Ganguly and Rao⁸ have shown that PAS is an effective tool for studying amorphous materials, since only the absorbed light is converted into heat (or the PA signal) and the scattered light does not pose any serious problem.

PA spectra of several arsenic chalcogenide glasses have been investigated in this laboratory¹⁶

and the study has provided absorption edges of these materials. The thermal coefficients of the absorption edges have been obtained by recording temperature-dependent PAS. In Fig. 9, we show the normalised PA spectra of amorphous and crystalline As_2S_3 and As_2Se_3 . There is a steep rise in photo-absorption in the 500-600 nm region. The

Fig. 9. Normalised PA spectrum of As_2S_3 and As_2Se_3 .

absorption edges are rather smeared out in the case of amorphous materials. We have taken 90% maximum normalised intensities to represent the band energies and these values correspond well with the reported data. The edge energies for the crystalline phases are higher than for the glasses. This is because the greater spread of the non-bonding levels of the chalcogenides in the glassy state which constitute the top of the valence band. Temperature-dependent PA spectra of As_2S_3 glass indicate a red shift consistent with the earlier observation by Young¹⁷. The thermal coefficient of the band edge energy calculated from temperature-dependent PAS measurements gives a value $7.1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ eVK}^{-1}$ which is in good agreement with the reported value of $7.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ eVK}^{-1}$.

Phase transitions in solids :

PA effect depends not only on optical but also on thermal properties of the material. The thermal diffusion length, μ_1 , which gives the distance from which heat can diffuse to the surface and produce a PA signal is given by,

$$\mu_1 = \left(\frac{k_1}{\pi \rho_1 C_1 f} \right)^{1/2} \quad (11)$$

During a phase transition the thermal properties change continuously or abruptly. These changes are manifested by a change in the PA amplitude. Monitoring the PA amplitude as a function of temperature should therefore provide information about the phase transition. We have investigated¹⁸ several first and second order phase transitions in

solids and compared our experimental results with the predictions of the RG model based on the known changes in specific heat and thermal diffusivity. The PA signal at a second order transition for a thermally thick material behaves as $C_1^{-1/2}$ or C_1^{-1} depending upon whether the material is optically opaque or not. This dependence is based on the assumption that k_1 does not change during a transition, and this does not always hold. We can derive an equation for α_1 considering the changes in k_1 and other factors¹⁹,

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{1}{3} \bar{v}_0 \bar{l}_0 \quad (12)$$

where \bar{v}_0 and \bar{l}_0 are the average sound velocity and average mean-free path of phonons, respectively in the solid. This equation indicates that a PA signal which depends on α_1 should be influenced by \bar{v}_0 and \bar{l}_0 . Our studies have shown that changes in the PA amplitude are dominated by C_1 changes; α_1 also plays a decisive role.

Sodium nitrite undergoes a first order transition from a ferroelectric to an incommensurate anti-ferroelectric phase at 437 K followed by a second order transition to a paraelectric phase at 438 K. These phase transitions were followed at 360 and 400 nm with single crystal as well as polycrystalline samples. The transitions were clearly seen both while heating and cooling and were separated by 2° in the cooling run. After temperature and amplitude normalisation, the PA curves showed nearly the same behaviour (Fig. 10). Particle size of the material does not seem to affect the phase transition to any measurable extent.

Cobalt monoxide undergoes antiferromagnetic ordering at the Neel temperature of 290 K. We have followed this transition for powdered CoO using white light. There was no temperature hysteresis and the transition was clearly seen both while heating and cooling. Comparison of the PA amplitude with the actual changes²⁰ in C_1 and α_1 show that the curve fits well with an $\alpha_1^{1/2}$ behaviour (Fig. 11).

First order transitions have also been studied using the PA effect. The first order transition of $CsNO_3$ has been followed by mixing it with carbon black and using white light. Comparison of the reported values with the experimental results show that the observed curve fits better with a $C_1^{-1/2}$ dependence (Fig. 12). Our studies show that there is no direct correlation between latent heat changes and PA amplitude changes accompanying phase transitions in solids.

Surface studies :

PAS can give information about the species adsorbed on solid surfaces provided the substrate is a non-absorbing substance, such as alumina or silica. A few monolayers of the chemisorbed species do not show saturation effects. We have exploited these

Fig. 10. I_{PA} vs T plots for NaNO_2 , as obtained (a) without any corrections and (b) after corrections for temperature and amplitude changes. (A) single crystal at 360 nm, (B) single crystal at 400 nm, (C) powdered single crystal at 360 nm, and (D) commercial sample with carbon black and using white light

Fig. 11. Comparison of I_{PA} vs T with $\alpha_1^{1/2}$ vs T for CoO (powder): (—) I_{PA} vs T plot, (···) $\alpha_1^{1/2}$ vs T for data of Salamon *et al.*²⁰, and (---) $\alpha_1^{1/2}$ vs T for data of Zhuze *et al.*¹⁹.

Fig. 12. (a) Plot of I_{PA} vs T for powdered CsNO_3 , (b) Plot of I_{PA} vs T for same sample (---) compared with C_1^{-1} vs T (···) and $C_1^{-1/2}$ vs T (—), and (c) differential scanning calorimeter trace of the same sample.

factors to investigate surface properties, such as surface area, surface acidity and metal states.

Adsorption of dyes on commercial activated alumina and chromatographic alumina (B.D.H.) possessing different surface areas has been examined²¹ to show the surface sensitivity of PAS. Dye solutions of varying concentration were added to weighed quantities of the alumina samples and the solids filtered off after equilibration. The solid was transferred into a PA cell and the spectrum recorded. The normalised PA intensity at 580 nm per unit weight of the solid increased with increase in dye (crystal violet) concentration reaching a maximum constant value corresponding to a maximum coverage. The ratio of the intensity values for the two samples was 4.7. Visible absorption spectroscopy was employed to check whether the ratio represents the real surface area². Thus, a decrease in the concentration of the supernatant dye solution after adsorption Δm and equilibrium concentration, m , could be fitted into a Langmuir equation,

$$\frac{m}{\Delta m} = \frac{m}{\Delta m_{\max}} + \frac{m}{K \Delta m_{\max}} \quad (13)$$

from the plots of $(m/\Delta m)$ vs m , the amount adsorbed for complete monolayer coverage Δm_{\max} and hence the surface area was calculated using a value of 90 \AA^2 for the molecular area of the dye crystal violet. The estimated surface areas were 179 and $39 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for activated and B.D.H. alumina,

respectively with a ratio 4.6, indicating that PAS intensity ratios are real and represent real surface area ratios (Fig. 13).

Fig. 13. Plot of I_{PA} vs fraction covered, θ , for two different alumina samples: (a) commercial alumina, and (b) chromatographic alumina.

In view of the surface sensitivity of PAS, we considered it valuable to investigate the possibility of using the technique for determining acidities of surfaces²². Experimentally, the procedure involves adding dry benzene (2 ml) to a pre-weighed (~0.2 g) amount of the catalyst followed by the addition of the indicator solution (0.5 ml) (in dry benzene). Solutions of n-butylamine in benzene were then added in varying amounts and equilibrated for 1 h with intermittent shaking. The spectra were recorded for the slurries in the PA cell. With bromocresol green indicator, there is only one band at 420 nm in 1% silica-alumina, whereas for 10% silica-alumina, there is one band at 550 nm corresponding to the acid form of the first titration range (lower pK_{HB+}). In the second titration range, we observe a band maximum at 600 nm corresponding to the base form whereas the band at 420 nm now corresponds to the acid form. The spectra at various titration ranges are shown in the Fig. 14. Using this procedure, we have carried out a systematic study of the acidity distribution in a series of silica-alumina samples by PAS and the results are shown in Fig. 15. These distributions correspond well with those found by other techniques.

We have also employed PAS for the study of surface metal states. Alumina samples impregnated with nickel nitrate solutions were heated separately at 110, 400, 600 and 800° and the PA spectra recorded at room temperature. The spectral data indicate that at 110° the sample resembles NiO, whereas other samples show a peak at 580 nm which progressively increases with the treatment temperature. This can be attributed to the increased Ni diffusion into the bulk. To check this, we have adsorbed dimethylglyoxime (DMG) over the surfaces. The Ni-DMG peak decreased to half its value at 400° (relative to 110°) indicating that only surface Ni can

Fig. 14. Normalised PA spectra of bromocresol green adsorbed on (a) silica-alumina (1%), and (b) silica-alumina (10%) with different amounts of n-butylamine in mmol g^{-1} of the solid (indicated against each curve).

Fig. 15. Plots of the n butylamine titre against the Hammett acidity function, H_0 , for (a) silica, and (b) to (e) silica-alumina samples with different alumina contents: (b) 0.1; (c) 1.0; (d) 3.5 and (e) 10.0 wt%.

bond with DMG and their diffusion into bulk reduces the intensity of the Ni-DMG peak. The basicity of Na₂O-alumina samples have been determined²³ with the adsorption of phenolphthalein

indicator. These successes indicate the potential use of PAS for surface studies.

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